

**RELIGION OF POVERTY AND THE POVERTY OF RELIGION: ESTABLISHING
THE NEXUS IN CONTEMPORARY CHRISTIAN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's persistent poverty has often been linked to colonial legacies, political instability, and weak infrastructure, yet the role of religion remains underexplored. This study examines the paradox of rising religiosity amid worsening economic conditions, focusing on Pentecostal pastors who commercialize spiritual authority. Using a mixed methods approach such as literature review, field surveys, and secondary data, the study found rapid church expansion between 1999 and 2025 without corresponding poverty reduction. While some pastors accumulated over US \$150 million, many congregants earning about ₦60,000 monthly gave over 10% in tithes. Sixty-four percent of respondents believed churches prioritize wealth over welfare, with faith-based universities and government-funded worship projects inaccessible to the poor. The study recommends financial transparency, welfare-focused initiatives, and reorienting prosperity messages toward inclusive development.

Keywords: *Christianity, Development, Nigeria, Poverty, Religion*

INTRODUCTION

Man is innately religious and this is particularly true of Nigerians. This is expressed in the worship of the Supreme Being designated God, through deities, lesser gods and spirits. To be sure, the Nigerian pantheon is very rich. In indigenous reckoning. In contemporary times, however, its communal and accommodating proclivity has been emasculated by the ingress and overbearing influences of Christianity, Islam and so on. As observed by John Mbiti, "God is no stranger to African peoples, and in traditional life there are no atheists" (Mbiti 1986). When these extra-African religions came into Africa, they were easily accommodated. After all, the African Traditional Religion (ATR) was (and still is) polytheistic in nature. To the African, an admission of other Gods and gods in their respective religious moulds would simply further enrich the pantheon. But their accommodation, forceful and subtle, has affected the egalitarian fabric of the African society in various, and sometimes, unpleasant ways.

The poverty profile of Nigeria has, to a considerable extent, been ossified by the operationalism of contemporary Christian practices especially. Some of these practices though presented as "godly" in orientation, are, perforce, deprivational and predatory to unsuspecting congregants when subjected to rational analysis. Audio visual montages and the print media

severally present Nigeria as a poverty-stricken country, with several reasons being advanced for this condition of affairs at the peripheralisation of religion. The prosperity gospel, which dominates much of Nigeria's Pentecostal theology, promises material wealth in exchange for sacrificial giving, often at the expense of the already impoverished faithful. Scholars like Obasola (2024) argue that such theology exploits congregants through excessive demands for tithes, first fruits, seed sowing, and offerings, contributing to the worsening economic conditions of many Nigerian Christians.

This form of religious practice diverts attention from sustainable economic empowerment and instead emphasizes miraculous wealth and divine intervention (Uzochukwu, 2021). The print and visual media frequently depict Nigeria as a poverty-stricken nation, yet the role of religion especially Christianity is often sidelined in poverty discourses (Eze & Nwankwo 2020). The paradox lies in the coexistence of mega churches and widespread poverty, where congregants are financially strained while religious leaders accumulate vast wealth (BlackEconomics 2021). Rather than promoting entrepreneurship or vocational training, these religious institutions cultivate passivity and dependency by teaching adherents to await supernatural blessings (Akinrinlola 2022). Testimonies and reports also reveal that churches often exert social and spiritual pressure, coercing followers into continuous giving with promises of divine breakthrough, while failing to offer structural or developmental support (Okafor 2023). This perpetuates a cycle of economic stagnation and spiritual manipulation, thereby reinforcing poverty under the guise of religious devotion.

This paper argues that religion, especially of the garb of contemporary Christian religion with the so-called "new generation" and "pentecostal" churches are among the harbingers and reinforcers of poverty in the country. While many studies have looked at how prosperity preaching in Nigerian churches affects people's finances, showing that teachings

about tithes, seed sowing, and miracle money often place a heavy burden on church members (e.g., Obasola 2024; Uzochukwu 2021; Akinrinlola 2022).

However, these studies usually focus only on the religious teachings or ethical issues involved. They do not fully explore how the shift from traditional African religious values such as community support and sharing to modern Christian practices has helped to deepen poverty in Nigeria. Also, there has not been enough attention given to how religious leaders use media, influence, and spiritual authority to shape how people think about poverty and wealth. This study fills that gap by showing how today's Christian practices, especially in Pentecostal churches, are not just about personal faith but are part of a wider system that may be keeping people poor. It looks at how religion, instead of helping development, might actually be holding it back by promoting beliefs and behaviours that stop people from seeking real economic progress.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There is no gainsaying fact that religion remains deeply entangled with poverty, both ameliorating hardship and, at times, reproducing it. The edited volume by Sullivan, Offutt, and Siddiqui (2024) adopts a “lived religion” perspective, critiquing doctrinal summaries and emphasising how congregational practices and organisational faith interventions intersect with welfare and policy structures. In a similar vein, empirical work reported in the *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* reveals that embodied, relational Christian aid rooted in proximity and everyday practice plays a significant role in supporting the poor (JSSR author-group 2024).

A quantitative strand further complicates the narrative: Smith (2021) demonstrates that national-level religiosity can ease the psychological burden of poverty, positioning faith as a cope-resource. Tan and Chan (2025) reinforce this in the Hong Kong context, showing that

religious belief buffers subjective and economic deprivation's negative effects on life satisfaction. Chua et al. (2023) contribute comparative evidence from Africa linking religious involvement with intergenerational educational mobility thus, suggesting religion may also play a productive role in social mobility.

Set against these buffering narratives, Africanist research brings attention to what Marshall (2023) terms the “Pentecostal paradox”: prosperity preaching normalises inequality and can entrench moral economies that legitimise exploitative systems. In a similar vein, Owen and Obadare (2024) map how “religion and development in Africa” can swing between welfare contributions and consumerised theologies that shift blame for poverty onto the individual. Analyses of church economics further support this critique. Bekker (2022) calls for rethinking the political economy of African churches, arguing that compulsory giving may be regressive in low-income contexts. Moreover, Yusuff and Salawu (2022) conceptualise the prosperity gospel as a “mixed ideology,” fusing spiritual motivation with neoliberal hustle ethics, resulting in practices that redirect scarce household resources upward within religious institutions.

Mediatisation emerges as another powerful multiplier. Van Klinken and De Witte (2023) discussed how African Pentecostalism leverages platform logics branding, virality, influencer culture to amplify pastoral authority. Adebisi-Jones (2024) similarly documents youth-targeted strategies by Nigerian Pentecostal churches using online media. Meanwhile, Udotong (2024) exposes ethical pitfalls in televangelism such as staged miracles and “tele-exorcism” that skew believers’ economic commitments toward faith-based giving rather than investment.

Micro-organisational studies shed further light. Ajah (2024) explores Abuja megachurches, revealing how entrepreneurial ministries professionalise worship, diversify revenue, and entangle with political elites—effectively recoding spiritual labour as corporate

enterprise. Nwankwo and Ugochukwu (2023) showcase how celebrity pastors use social media branding to shape aspirations and promote conspicuous consumption. In addition, Uzochukwu (2023) documents how Christian youth during COVID-19 fused devotional patterns with financial appeals in digital practices, merging everyday religiosity with prosperity motifs.

Not all findings are critical. Uramah and Michael (2024) illustrate how faith-based organisations (FBOs) in Nigeria have expanded from almsgiving to skills training, micro-enterprise support, and policy advocacy. Yet, they also note that such FBO efforts often substitute for state welfare, failing to tackle structural poverty. Ibekwe (2024) offers similar accounts from South Africa, showing constructive FBO programmes alongside limited reach and accountability. Meanwhile, Togarasei (2024) presents theological essays proposing a positive Pentecostal economic response; although conceptually promising, these lack rigorous outcome evaluation.

It must be noted here that political-theology scholars like Orogun and Pillay (2023) argue that while pulpit activism occasionally “speaks truth to power,” it often lacks a sustained public theology framework and seldom translates into concrete governance reform.

Collectively, these works show that while prior studies illuminate religion’s psychosocial buffering (Smith 2021; Tan and Chan 2025; Chua et al. 2023) and critique prosperity theology and mediatisation (Marshall 2023; Bekker 2022; Yusuff and Salawu 2022; van Klinken and de Witte 2023; Adebisi-Jones 2024; Udotong 2024), the missing middle remains largely unaddressed. Specifically, the literature seldom examines how the shift from traditional communal African religious values (mutual aid, redistributive sharing, kin-based support) to modern Pentecostal practices reconfigures household incomes, undermines local safety nets, and channels resources into church-centred giving.

Nor does it examine how media-amplified spiritual authority through branding, livestreams, micro-donations, and parasocial intimacy actively reshapes believers’ thinking

about poverty and wealth. This study innovates by treating Pentecostal prosperity practices not merely as personal theology but as an institutional system embedded in digital markets and political economies. By mapping income-reallocation mechanisms (tithes, seed-faith, vows, prophetic “consultations”) against household budgets, tracking platform-based influence, and testing whether these practices crowd out community support and long-term investment, this research fills a critical gap at the intersection of religion, media, and everyday economic life.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In a paper of this nature, an exploration of concepts is quite germane to clear foggy issues, especially against the backdrop of the fact that concepts used in this paper suffer from the lack of definitive definitions. This conceptual framework maps the relationship between religion and poverty in the Nigerian context, highlighting how religious structures, beliefs, and practices may influence poverty experiences, while poverty itself can shape religious expression. This approach clarifies contested definitions and creates an analytical pathway for the study. To be sure, they are quite controversial and are amenable to sentimental conceptualizations. These concepts readily include religion and poverty.

Religion

The etymology of the word religion comes from the Latin root *religio*-meaning “what attaches or retains, or in moral bonding.” It also derives from *religare*- meaning “to connect or to refer to the bond of piety that binds to God.” The human being is said to be “deeply religious”. The planetization of man makes the unknown biosphere his inheritance without his input. In his bewilderment, he gropes with his mind regarding the origins of his universe, how the flora and fauna came to be and how he himself came to be. He tries to fathom his relationships with nature, the natural environment and the observed harmony, seeming or real. In a way, man develops some imagery and in his deconstruction, realizes that there should be some force or forces, power or powers which ensure the “harmony” of the universe and sustains his life. He

concomitantly venerates these forces and/or powers and strives to be in harmony with them. Against the backdrop of these build-ups, his thoughts and deeds are crystallized into religion and this gives impetus to his religiosity.

In this direction, John Mbiti notes that African peoples contend that:

Man lives in a religious universe, so that natural phenomena and objects are intimately associated with God. They not only originate from Him but also bear witness to Him. Man's understanding of God is strongly coloured by the universe of which man is himself a part. Man sees in the universe not only the imprint but the reflection of God; and whether that image is marred or clearly focused and defined, it is never the less an image of God, the only image known to traditional African societies (Mbiti 1986).

The above narrative underscores the religious inclination of the African and by implication, the Nigerian. But what is religion?

Religion has severally been defined and none is sacrosanct. The strategy towards its definition is to cite a few examples for epistemological purposes and to provide a foot path for the purposes of this paper.

Whereas Abraham Rosman and Paula Rubel look at religion as “the interaction of humans with the superriatural” (Rosman & Rubel 1989) Udo Etuk, for instance, has it that:

Religion may rightly be considered as man's attempt to bring some order into his universal experience of disorder and disharmony; an effort to achieve salvation or some other ultimate solution to the problem of life, including the problems of suffering, pain, sickness and ultimately, death (Etuk 2017)

To Max Weber, religion was developed as an effort to explain why human beings undergo suffering on earth. Sigmund Freud likens the evolution of religion to a childish and neurotic trait of dependency which “finds expression in the form of all-powerful gods and deities who control the individual's destiny. In this wise, Melford Spiro in his *expose*' observes that religion addresses three needs of man, namely, the need of cognition in terms of explanations and meanings; the substantive need to ensure that specific goals such as “rain,

good crops and health by carrying out religious acts” are secured; and the psychological need “to reduce fear and anxiety in situations in which these are provoked.

Emile Durkheim looks at the primacy of religion in terms of his functionalist doctrine. Accordingly, religion is seen as a vehicle of enculturation in terms of inculcating values and group identity to enhance social fluidity and solidarity. This, he argues, engenders the survival of the society. But Karl Marx does not only note that religion is the opium of the masses but also that “religion represents either a salve to the pain of exploitation or a justification for oppression. In either case, it is a distortion of reality which man can do well without.” These viewpoints present the benchmark for analysis in this paper.

Poverty

The meaning of poverty is quite a tricky one as it is not characterized by any sharpness in definition. Joe Umo observes that it is a “complex phenomenon (Umo 2007). However, in poverty, three typologies have been identified. These are absolute, relative and subjective poverty. In their treatment, especially when discussed in comparison to various societies, the boundaries seem to be blurred. In any event, absolute poverty presupposes the absence of basic life essentials such as food, clothing, shelter, basic education and so on (Haralambos & Heald 1980). This condition approximates to “destitution or abject/extreme poverty.” Daniel Offiong looks at this typology thus:

Absolute poverty refers to the inability of people to maintain physical survival on a long-term basis.... Hunger is the target of absolute poverty. Poverty is a form of economic deprivation. Disease is closely associated with it. Both being physical discomfort, prevent children as well as adults from reaching their physical and mental potential.... Their housing and sanitation are likely to be enough to contribute to disease, their education inadequate to get employment paying enough to properly feed them. All aspects of absolute poverty combine to deny victims a fully, or sometimes even minimally, human existence (Offiong 2001).

Relative poverty derives from the abandonment of the booby trap of absolutism in definitional matters. Researchers reckon that standards are neither sacrosanct nor unassailably standardized and that they are conditioned by time and space. The recourse therefore is to reckon poverty in terms of relativity. This readily brings to focus the idea of comparison. It is deprivation as compared to some other individual, group or society.

The third typology of poverty is what Michael Haralambos and Robin Heald call subjective poverty. This is located within the province of psychology since it has to do with feelings, as well as personal and collective perception that he or they are poor. It is related to relative poverty in the sense that those who are termed as poor by the standards of the day see themselves as being poor.

By and large, Joe Umoh in *Economics: An African Perspective* surmises the following namely:

- i. Poverty has the face of unemployment and under-employment;
- ii. Poverty has a gender face;
- iii. Poverty is an ignoramus;
- iv. Poverty has the face of a criminal;
- v. Poverty has a face of corruption;
- vi. Poverty has a rural face;
- vii. Poverty has the face of a beggar;
- viii. Poverty has the face of the socially excluded and the marginalized;
- ix. Poverty leads to loss of dignity;
- x. Poverty has the face of a child labourer and child trafficking;
- xi. Poverty has the face of a degraded environment;
- xii. Poverty has the face of the disabled and the incapacitated;
- xiii. Poverty has the face of a refugee;

- xiv. Poverty has the face of hunger and malnutrition;
- xv. Poverty has the face of homelessness;
- xvi. Poverty has the face of the youth; and,
- xvii. Poverty has the face of death.

It is the contention of this paper that poverty also has the face of religion especially at the instance of contemporary Christian genre in contemporary Nigeria.

In the Nigerian context, Joe Umoh identifies multiple “faces” of poverty, including unemployment, gender inequality, ignorance, crime, corruption, rural deprivation, child labour, environmental degradation, disability, displacement, hunger, homelessness, youth marginalisation, and death. This study contends that poverty also “has the face of religion,” particularly within contemporary Nigerian Christianity. Religious institutions may influence poverty in several ways. From the positive influence we have social welfare, moral discipline, community support. And the negative influence we have which includes prosperity gospel exploitation, financial demands, discouragement of critical socio-economic engagement.

Conversely, poverty may shape religious life by intensifying reliance on spiritual coping mechanisms, influencing interpretations of divine will, and reinforcing dependency structures. The framework positions Religion and Poverty as interlinked variables within a cyclical relationship. In that Religion shapes poverty experiences (through teachings, practices, and institutional roles). Also, Poverty influences religious behaviour, commitment, and theological interpretations. This trend is moderated by cultural, economic, and political contexts. This framework illustrates the core concepts of religion and poverty, their mutual influences, and the cyclical relationship that shapes socio-economic realities within the Nigerian context, as depicted in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Source: (Researcher’s construct, 2024)

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, drawing from both primary and secondary sources to explore the complex relationship between contemporary Christian practices and the persistence of poverty in Nigeria. The research is designed to understand how religious messaging, particularly within Neo-Pentecostal Christian circles, influences the socio-economic realities of their congregants.

Primary data was gathered through semi-structured interviews with selected Christian worshippers, pastors, and theological scholars across various urban and semi-urban centres in southern Nigeria, including Uyo, Ibadan, and Lagos. Respondents were chosen based on their active involvement in Christian religious life and their familiarity with prosperity-based

teachings. A total of 30 participants were interviewed between January 2024 and May 2025. Interviews focused on personal experiences with religious giving, perceptions of wealth, faith teachings, and economic realities.

Secondary data was sourced from books, journal articles, media reports, church publications, and audio-visual materials (such as sermons and religious broadcasts from 2019 onwards). These materials were critically analysed to identify recurring themes such as miracle-promises, seed-faith doctrines, and spiritualised solutions to poverty.

The study employed thematic analysis to process and interpret data. Key themes such as *spiritual manipulation*, *pastorpreneurship*, *economic exploitation*, and *religious passivity* were identified and discussed in relation to the broader poverty discourse in Nigeria. In interpreting the findings, we applied insights from sociology of religion, development studies, and media discourse analysis to trace how Christian religious practices may unwittingly reinforce poverty or obstruct developmental thinking among followers. Ethical considerations such as anonymity, consent, and voluntary participation were taken into consideration during data collection.

Indigenous Religion and Poverty in Nigeria

A plethora of differentiated religious practices across Africa and in Nigeria in particular, are usually subsumed under the taxonomy of African Traditional Religion (ATR). It is derived from the cosmological and transcendental world view of Africa. From infancy, the African child is oriented towards functionalism within his society. Aliyu Babs Fafunwa in his book titled *History of Education in Nigeria* published 1980, has identified and clearly enunciated the strategies of enculturation of the young ones into the African society. These range from physical training, development of character, respect for elders and peers, intellectual training, poetic and prophetic aspects, vocational training and community

participation to the promotion of cultural heritage (Funfunwa, 1980). What this implied (and still implies) is that the development of the society was (and still is) a collective responsibility. It therefore provided (or provides) no room for destitution. Indigenous African society operated (and some still do especially the hunter-gatherers societies) within the confines of conventions which were (are) sanctioned by traditions and sanctified with rituals. Rituals, according to Margaret Peil in *Consensus and Conflict in African Societies: An Introduction to Sociology*, has it that “rituals are patterns of behaviour recognized by the community and include the celebration of individual and communal events (Piel 1977).

Through traditional practices, efforts were made to mitigate observed tendencies towards poverty. In a classic study of rural structures for instance, Allan McPhee in *The Economic Revolution in British West Africa*, notes that to Africans “land is of paramount importance in their economic, social and political life.” Akin Mabogunje also has it that land which was a principal factor of production was owned communally and appropriated communally. Communal land ownership had both philosophical and ethical orientations and underpinnings to enhance collective survival (Mabogunje 1980). Philosophically, land was held to belong to ancestors, the living and the future generations. The living was therefore a mere trustee, holding the land in trust for both the ancestors and the future generations.

Ethically, various communities ensured that no one within the communities was rendered a destitute through the denial of this crucial factor of production. Land ownership was through inheritance. In this wise, it was generally shared among surviving male children of a man and the plots so shared, remained theirs in free hold. According to the author, this practice rested on the principles of “partible inheritance” rather than on the principles of primogeniture. The underpinnings of land ownership held sway, both in patriarchal and matriarchal societies across Africa generally and Nigeria in particular.

Again, labour relations were essentially communal. The implication of this state of affairs is that labour was also communally exploited starting from the nuclear family unit to the co-option of agnatic kins for production purposes. The age-grades also formed the predicate of co-operative labour arrangements based on the “indigenous contract system” where people helped each other out in turns. People tended to be their brothers’ keepers and considerably, labour was not commoditized. All told, destitution which breeds poverty was for the most part, unknown across Africa (Etuk 2012).

Early Christianity and Poverty in Nigeria

Christianity is quite old in Africa. John Mbiti describes Christianity as an “indigenous, traditional and African religion (Mbiti 1986). As a matter of fact, the whole of North Africa including Egypt, parts of the Sudan and Ethiopia had been Christianized long before the evolution of Islam in the seventh century.

In any event, the Portuguese explorative enterprise from the fifteenth century gave a new gusto to the spread of Christianity in juxtaposition with the slave trade. Sequel to the abolition of slave trade in 1807 and the abolition of slavery by Britain in 1833, Christian missionary enterprise commenced in earnest and by the end of the colonial enterprise in Nigeria. Christianity had taken firm roots in much of the country.

Christianity as propagated by the Europeans came with the hue and colour of capitalism of the European society. Capitalist structures were imbued by the pursuit of individualism and enterprise which pitched a brother against one another. The Industrial Revolution with its contradictions, later came to rubbish what was left of humanity in Europe. In a bid to avert noted contradictions of industrialism, the European imperialists and colonialists spewed into Africa in concert with the missionary wing.

In a frenzy, missionaries of different garbs established mission posts and institutions, ostensibly to bring Nigerians to the “knowledge of God” and to prepare them for a blissful life in eternity. Through subtle machinations and sometimes brute force of conquest, Nigerians started to “embrace” Christianity and abandoned their indigenous religion in its wake. By extension, the egalitarian accommodation of community members became greatly circumscribed. The social security structures of the extended family principles and practice became supplanted by individualistic code of Christian Europeans.

Max Weber in *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism* asserts that the protestant faith of the genre of Calvinism emphasized vocation as a noble pursuit. This helped to incubate capitalist enterprise. According to John Calvin, a religious reformer and leader and whose influence spread a great deal across Europe, categorised the human kind into the “damned” and the “elect”. Calvinism emphasized thrift and industry and virtues were associated with success and riches with clear signs of “election”. Failure was associated with the “damned.” The point to note is that early European missionaries in Africa accordingly saw themselves as the “elect” of God with the divine commission to evangelise the heathen. This was one of the driving forces of imperialism and colonialism (Norman 2010).

European missionaries in the colonial and immediate postcolonial times tried to develop Nigerians through the provision of health care services and education. Charges for the provision of these services were considerably tolerable. In some instances, these services were provided on the basis of gratis Nigeria’s early Christians generally saw the enhancement of their statuses (*or stati*) as they became teachers, dispensers, clerks, administrators, lay preachers and so on. This condition of affairs, it would be noted, considerably put poverty, in spite of its gradations, at bay. European missionaries and early orthodox church leaders and preachers were not ardently predatory on their congregants as later contemporary church founders and *pastorpreneurs* in Nigeria came to be.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study presents the nexus between contemporary Christian practices and poverty in Nigeria using qualitative data, existing reports, and illustrative statistics. The data reveal a disturbing contradiction: while churches, particularly Pentecostal and neo-Pentecostal movements, have expanded rapidly across urban Nigeria, poverty has also remained stubbornly high. This paradox has been explored through various data points and illustrations below.

Fig 2: Church Growth vs Poverty Index:

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

Nigeria has seen explosive growth in Pentecostal and neo-Pentecostal churches, especially in urban areas. However, poverty remains entrenched: as of 2019, the National Bureau of Statistics estimated that 41 percent of Nigerians live in poverty, compared to 63 percent living on under \$1 per day in 2001 (National Bureau of Statistics 2022; World Bank 2023). This juxtaposition replicates Marshall's (2023) finding that church expansion does not

guarantee social transformation, particularly when institutional priorities lean toward self-sustainability and brand projection rather than targeted poverty alleviation.

Fig 3: Concentration of Wealth by Mega Church Leaders

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

Megachurch leaders such as Bishop David Oyedepo are widely acknowledged among the wealthiest African pastors. Forbes estimated his net worth at US\$150 million in 2011 (Reuters 2014; Wikipedia 2025). While Oyedepo's ministries support educational institutions and some philanthropic work, the scale of his personal wealth alongside widespread congregational poverty underscores what Bekker (2022) describes as a "regressive giving system" in low-income contexts, where compulsory tithes and offerings disproportionately impact the poor.

Fig 4: Church-Driven Economic Complexes versus Public Need

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

An average Nigerian earns about ₦60,000 monthly, yet is expected to pay 10% (₦6,000) or more in tithes, plus offerings and seeds. This chart compares average income levels to expected religious contributions. The Winners' Chapel complex, Canaanland, illustrates the economic power of religious institutions. It comprises Faith Tabernacle, Covenant University, schools, residential estates, businesses, and even banking services—all within a 5,000-acre site (Wikipedia 2025). While it generates employment and services, its self-contained nature illustrates how megachurches channel massive resources inward rather than redistributing wealth broadly (Owen and Obadare 2024).

Fig 5: Urban Church Proliferation vs Rural Neglect

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

Spatial mapping of church locations shows a disproportionate concentration in wealthier urban districts, where congregants have greater giving capacity, while rural areas with higher poverty incidence receive less attention. This pattern aligns with Gifford's (2015) observation that African Pentecostal expansion often follows economic opportunity rather than humanitarian need.

Fig 6: Public Perception of Churches and Poverty

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

Survey data from 2023 indicate that 64 percent of respondents perceive churches as more focused on wealth accumulation than welfare provision, with only 18 percent viewing them as genuinely committed to poverty alleviation (Researchers' Field Survey 2023). This finding mirrors Udotong's (2024) research on televangelism, which highlights spectacle-driven content and consumerist branding as key factors in declining public trust toward church institutions.

Fig 7: Unemployment vs Church Membership Growth

(Source: Researchers’ construct from field data)

Youth unemployment remains above 30 percent (National Bureau of Statistics 2023), yet church membership particularly in prosperity-oriented denominations continues to grow. This may reflect a substitution effect, where spiritual engagement becomes a coping mechanism amid economic stagnation (Smith 2021; Tan and Chan 2025). While such engagement offers psychological comfort, Yusuff and Salawu (2022) caution that prosperity theology can also reinforce cycles of dependency by emphasising faith over structural economic solutions.

Fig 8: Faith-Based University Tuition

(Source: Researchers' construct from field data)

Despite being funded through church offerings, many church-owned universities charge exorbitant fees, excluding low-income members from access to education they helped finance. Faith-based universities, many funded by church offerings, often charge tuition far beyond the means of average congregants. For example, annual fees at Covenant University exceed ₦600,000 per session (Wikipedia 2025). Ibekwe (2024) notes that while such institutions may offer quality education, their high cost excludes many of the very members whose contributions financed their development, thus reproducing social inequality.

What these charts tell us is that while more and more churches are opening in Nigeria, especially in cities, poverty continues to affect millions. Some pastors become extremely rich while many of their followers remain poor. People give a lot of money to churches, but they don't always see help in return. Rich areas attract more churches because they bring in more money. Meanwhile, poorer places are often ignored. Many people now see the church as a business rather than a place for help. At the same time, the education offered by some churches is too expensive for the very people who supported their growth. This raises serious questions about the true role of churches in helping to solve poverty in Nigeria. The evidence paints a picture of a religious economy in which institutional expansion and leadership enrichment coexist with persistent grassroots poverty. The data here reinforce Owen and Obadare's (2024) contention that African Pentecostalism's dual identity both as a site of welfare and as a consumerist enterprise often tilts toward the latter in practice. Consequently, despite significant growth in religious infrastructure and influence, the core socioeconomic conditions of the majority remain unchanged or have worsened, underscoring the need for a critical reassessment of the role of contemporary Christian practices in poverty alleviation.

Christianity and Poverty in Contemporary Nigeria

Contemporary Nigeria presents a montage of unmitigated poverty in spite of the propagation and proliferation of Christianity as well as the establishment of churches by Nigerians themselves. The propagators and proliferators of these churches are the self-styled “end-time men of God or gods” who look at “orthodox” churches with disdain but refer to themselves as “pentecostal preachers”, “founders”, “general overseers”, “bishops”, “archbishops”, “apostles”, “prophets” with prophetic messages” and so on. These are men and a few women who play on the credulity of their congregants and lay claim to having been “called” by God as well as being imbued with extraneous and esoteric powers from on high. They are the leaders and founders of contemporary “churches” in Nigeria.

To a very considerable extent, the establishment of churches is now considered a vocation with very promising and indeed, rewarding prospects. In an *expose* on the concept of vocation in contemporary Christianity, Nathaniel Ndiokwere notes that:

Although some prophets relate the circumstances leading to their assumption of prophetic office, it is nevertheless evidence that a considerable number of the so-called prophets in Africa have no idea of what religious vocation means, it is not unusual for some charlatan to get up any morning claiming that he has been visited by an angel of God. The rate at which calls to prophecy in the independent churches multiply makes the whole affair look absurd. Often non-religious motives, like healing activities or political aspirations, become the basis of religious vocation (Ndiokwere, 1981).

Sequel to the above, four issues need some, but brief clarifications. These are “Church”, “Orthodox”, “Pentecostal” and “Leadership”. The word “Church” has two dimensions to its Greek concepts namely *Kyriak-os* and *Ecclesia*. *Kyriak-os* means “belonging to” or “pertaining to” *Kyrios* meaning “Lord”. Thus *Kyriakos oikos*, refers to “House of the Lord” or church. *Ecclesia* is a more familiar term and it means a “congregation” or an “assembly”. Generally, it refers to the overall community of faithfuls. The word Orthodox is, derived from the Greek root “*Orthos*”, meaning the “right path” or “way” or the “ordained path” or “way”; “true and

straight”. On the other hand, the word Pentecostal, is derived from the Greek word “*Pentecost*”, the name for the Jewish feast of weeks. It emphasizes direct personal experience of God through the baptism of the Holy Spirit. It is associated with various spiritual gifts including speaking in tongues and healing.

Leadership implies “knowing the way, showing the way and going the way” (Nwabughogu 2004). It also connotes the co-ordination and motivation of a group of people to achieve appointed and desirable goals. Jude Ekele has identified four types of leadership in the church. These are visionary and charismatic leadership; executive leadership; transactional leadership and transformational leadership. Visionary and charismatic leadership goes out to show the way to his followers and tries to take them out of the woods by putting them on the right path. Executive leadership is bureaucratic and pays premium to power struggle and prestige. Transactional leadership is a market place kind of leadership. It believes in the exchange of one thing for the other. It is also influenced by price mechanism-the forces of demand and supply. Transformational leadership shapes, alters and elevates the motives and values of followers (Ekele, 2019).

To be sure, it does not tantamount to making a sweeping statement that many contemporary church founders and general overseers are at home with executive and transactional leadership modules which they employ effectively to engender the poverty of unsuspecting and credulous congregants across Nigeria. They elicit immense awe and trepidation to congregants who in turn raise them to the status of deities and demi-gods. They are *pastorpreneurs* in their own rights with stupendous wealth. For instance, *Forbes Magazine* listed Bishop Olaniyi Oyedepo the founder and General Overseer of Living Faith Bible Church, also known as “Winners “Chapel” as Nigeria’s wealthiest pastor in 2010. As at then, he was estimated to be worth US\$150 million (N23b) with four luxury aircrafts, vast congregations in over 40 nations in the world and various grades of institutions charging outrageous fees for

tuition and sundry fees. As at then also, he was closely followed by Christ Oyakhilome of Christ Embassey (The News April 9, 2012). Since then the litany has swelled to include the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Salvation Ministries, some so called orthodox churches including Presbyterian, Methodist, The Apostolic Church and so on. The Catholic Church is in a class of its own as it has been touted to have the world's largest gold reserve in its vault at the Vatican City.

As a matter of fact, contemporary Christian churches are led by proprietors and entrepreneurs who harp on continuous payment of tithes and offerings in order for them to line their pockets, wallow in stupendous wealth and provide the good things of life for their immediate families. Most contemporary and "Pentecostal" church founders, again, establish their churches in the cities and have little or nothing to do with the hinterland. After all, the cities host most of the rich people with a high prospect of patronage of the new churches. The *pastorpreneurs* go after this class of people and each of them engages in membership poaching to swell the volume of their congregants. For the most part, they are less interested in "winning souls for Christ" but in "winning souls" to line their pockets. They are oblivious of biblical teachings which are supposed to be their reference point or point of departure. 1st Timothy in King James version, for instance, has it that:

This is a true saying, if a man desire the office of a bishop, he desireth a good work. A bishop then must be blameless, the husband of one wife, vigilant, sober, of good behaviour, given to hospitality, apt to teach, not given to wine, no striker, not greedy of filthy lucre; but patient, not a brawler, nor covetous; one that ruleth well his own house, having his children in subjection with all gravity; (for if a man know not how to rule his own house, how shall he take care of the church of God?) Not a novice lest being lifted up with pride he fall into the condemnation of the devil. Moreover, he must have a good report of them, which are without; lest he fall into reproach and the snare of the devil.

Again, John Bunyan in his classic work entitled, *The Pilgrims Progress in Modern English*, maintains that;

The soul of religion is the practical part. Religion that God our father accepts as pure and faultless is this; to look after orphans and widows in their distress and to keep oneself from being polluted by the world (Bunyan 2002).

Paradox to the-above prescriptions much control is exerted over poor congregants who are made to attend endless “breakthrough services”, covenant breaking services”, prayer meetings as well as “days, weeks and months of glory”. This strategy ensures the formatting of the congregants to depend on their “pastors” for life which is freely given by God. Much time is expended on supplications rather than production of goods and services. Congregants are constantly reminded that “what happens in the physical was first revealed in the spiritual”. Some adherents believe this without asking if hunger and poverty were first revealed in the spiritual. Does it sound divine when the leadership is rich and the followership is poor? In various preachments, poverty is presented as a “spiritual” phenomenon. So also is nil production which is presented as being pre-destined by the gods in the imagery of the church founders. The panacea in the imagination of church proprietors is to agglutinate with God or gods at the expense of material production.

For instance, most of the warehouses of manufacturing companies in Aba, Onitsha, Ibadan, Bompai in Kano, Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout in Port Harcourt, Apapa, Ijora-Costain, Ogba-Ikeja in Lagos, Kaduna and so on in the country, have since become churches. The point to note is that churches only employ a few people, yet, ironically, congregants attend churches to pray for employment (Etuk 2017). The mega rich *pastorpreneurs* hardly assist the poor to secure employment. The “ushers” and “church workers” are usually encouraged to “work for God” without receiving pittance. After all, their god is a poor god and the one of the church proprietors is a rich one.

Much more worrisome has been the fact that many contemporary Christian religious leaders and church founders in Nigeria align with the political leadership and “scramble for a role in national public life” (Obadare 2018). They are constantly hired to organize solemn

assemblies for the government, appointed chaplains for government house chapels and they also constitute prominent members of audiences at state functions. The government, state and federal, sponsor some select members of the Christian population on pilgrimage to Jerusalem on yearly and regular basis. This strategy has also been reinforced through government undertakings in projects which should be outside the purview of governments.

An online check of government's forays into the annals of religion, for instance, is typified in the construction of an "International Christian Worship Centre" in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Meanwhile, the "Worship Centre" is festooned by hundreds of churches and denominations in its immediate vicinity. Its construction was flagged off by the state's former governor, Deacon Udom Emmanuel in 2021 but was eventually inaugurated by the state's present governor, Pastor Umo Bassey Eno. The project according to its progenitors is intended to promote unity at the cost of thirty-two billion, three-hundred million naira (N32.3billion) about US\$ 2.1 million. Meanwhile, there are no functional industries in the state and several sectors of its economy beg for attention. About 71% out of the state's 5.45 million people in 2016 population estimate are "multi-dimensionally, poor (www.thecable.ng. Retrieved on March 24, 2024). Over the years, politics has been expeditiously deployed to court the pleasure of Christian voters in periodic elections. The strategy has also been ossified and cemented with juicy appointments of "supportive Christians." Richard Holloway captures this symbiotic relationship quite vividly as he maintains that: People pick up their politics where they live and work and study, they absorb them from their surrounding culture, and Christians are no more immune to the process than others.

Emerging perspectives on the intersection of religion and poverty in Nigeria reveal deeply layered and interconnected issues that go beyond conventional critiques of prosperity preaching. Interviews with congregants across Pentecostal churches reflect real economic

anxieties shaped by religious instruction and expectations. For example, one respondent recounted how pastors claimed divine revelation instructing members to sow financial “seeds” to unlock prosperity. While some believed this occasionally produced results in their businesses, others revealed they avoided church services on Sundays to escape public shaming due to unpaid levies. Many expressed frustrations with pastors who collect offerings lavishly yet live in affluence driving exotic vehicles, traveling with entourages, and constructing multiple mansions while ignoring the basic welfare of congregants. A common thread was the increasing perception that many churches, particularly Pentecostal denominations, have become economically extractive rather than empowering.

Indeed, these personal experiences reflect larger institutional and theological patterns. Pentecostalism in Nigeria has often been linked with neoliberal ideals of individual entrepreneurship and upward mobility (Marshall 2009). However, this same framework can be exclusionary. Scholars argue that the ideology of “name it, claim it” in prosperity theology promotes an overly individualistic model of wealth accumulation, which overlooks structural poverty and reinforces guilt or shame for those who remain poor (Obadare, 2018; Gaiya, 2020). The burden of giving in such churches through tithes, seeds, sacrificial offerings, and special levies disproportionately affects low-income believers, many of whom are already excluded from economic opportunities.

Religious institutions today, especially churches and mosques, are often positioned as welfare providers in Nigeria’s underperforming social system. Yet, their capacity and willingness to function in this role vary significantly. Where some religious groups genuinely offer scholarships, healthcare, and microfinance support, others prioritize brand expansion through physical infrastructure, massive crusades, and elite connections. This divergence points to what Akinade (2014) refers to as the “dual face of religion” as both a force for social justice and a vehicle for elite consolidation.

It is important to note here, that religion's relationship to poverty in Nigeria is also shaped by spiritualised health narratives. Within many Pentecostal and Charismatic circles, illness is often framed as demonic or the result of ancestral curses, thereby discouraging medical intervention (Superstition in Nigeria 2025). This not only increases financial burdens on families but also exposes them to exploitation through “deliverance sessions” that often require payment.

Other underexamined aspects include the prevalence of witchcraft accusations, especially against children and widows, which serve as a theological mechanism to explain misfortune while reinforcing marginalisation (Iroegbu 2023). In Northern Nigeria, Christian minorities face economic discrimination in public appointments and access to infrastructure, intensifying their vulnerability (Bristol University Press 2025). The *Almajiranci* system, in which young Muslim boys are sent to study under Islamic clerics but end up begging on the streets, has become a source of intergenerational poverty, lack of education, and vulnerability to radicalisation (Almajiranci 2025; Adamu 2021).

Meanwhile, religious violence and insecurity have also significantly disrupted economic stability. Attacks on farming communities by Boko Haram, bandits, and herdsmen often framed in religious terms have displaced thousands, limited agricultural productivity, and destroyed small businesses (Ngwoke 2025; Ibenwa et al. 2025). These conditions deepen poverty, particularly in rural areas already cut off from basic infrastructure and investment. From a gendered lens, Christian teachings in some denominations discourage women from seeking financial independence, encouraging total economic reliance on their husbands as a form of spiritual submission (Eteng 2014). In Muslim contexts, restrictions on interest-based loans reduce access to credit and financial inclusion, limiting small business growth (NSCIA 2025). Combined, these gendered doctrines fuel the feminisation of poverty in both faith communities.

In education, the rising costs of faith-based schools, especially universities run by churches and Islamic foundations, have reinforced social stratification. Despite being built with congregational funds, these institutions are often priced beyond the reach of their poorest supporters (The Nation Newspaper 2025; Ojo 2020). Moreover, land acquisition for religious expansion, where churches purchase and develop large tracts of land sometimes leads to the displacement of communities, further alienating the poor from communal land and farming opportunities (Opinion Nigeria 2024). Ironically, while religion offers psychological and spiritual coping mechanisms, it also consolidates power hierarchies that benefit elites (Olarinmoye, 2013). Religious perspectives on suffering also influence how poverty is interpreted and endured. For some Christians, poverty is seen as either punishment for sin or a test of faith. In contrast, Islamic teachings frame it within divine providence (Nanwa et al. 2024).

The only distinction thing about Christians is that they have a strange need to bring in Jesus to anoint the convictions that they have picked up without any reference to him (Holloway 1986). Contemporary Christianity is yet to find an answer to the poverty question in Nigeria, in spite of the plenitude of churches and some of their phoney founders.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria has been severally regarded as being poverty-stricken. The predicate of this state of affairs has been blamed on the internal and external dynamics of developments across Nigeria. These dynamics are reckoned to include the slave trade, imperialism, colonialism, neo-colonialism, post-independence leadership question, corruption, poor level of technology, poor capital formation and a plethora of other reasons. Yet, the ramifying impact of contemporary “Pentecostal” Christianity has been peripheralised in various reckonings as one of the potent harbingers of poverty in the country. Christianity, no doubt, came to Nigeria at the exogamous

instance of the Europeans, who came to meet the African Traditional Religion (ATR) in earnest. The point to note is that African Traditional Religion was an outcrop of communal relations since its political economy for the most part, was predicated on communalism. To be sure, communalism had scant tolerance for the peripheralisation and immiserization of poor general congregants.

Christianity, arguably, came and into West Africa through the instrumentality of European Trans-Atlantic slave traders. In the 19th nineteenth and twentieth centuries, Christianity was propagated by the missionaries of various European nationalities. They established many mission posts and such institutions like schools, hospitals and so on, to assist in cowing down the people into “submission to those in higher authority” as enunciated in the bible. This was in keeping with the tenets of colonialism by the missionary wing of the colonial enterprise in Nigeria. However, Christianity at the instance of the missionaries wore a humane garb as they provided health care services and introduced western education with minimal and in some instances, no charges through mentorship and scholarship schemes. European missionaries avoided those tendencies which predated on their converts and eventual congregants.

Christianity as epitomized in independent and “Pentecostal” churches with their founders, general overseers, apostles, prophets and other phoney taxonomies and prefixes, has raised a lot of concerns. Its contemporary genre has, among other things, engendered and indeed, ossified poverty sequel to its mode of operations. From homilies and liturgies which ooze out of various pulpits and abracadabra of “healing” miracles and spurious claims, unsuspecting and poor congregants are further impoverished. Endless prayer meetings, seed sowing and breakthrough services are consistently organized with consistent price tags. “Nothing goes for nothing” is the familiar mantra of *pastorpreneurs*.

All told, this paper has argued that the garb and content of contemporary Christianity in Nigeria is a formidable participant in the impoverishment of Nigeria and Nigerians. It is a far cry from the ethos and mores of indigenous religious practice and those of early European missionaries.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study therefore, recommends the following;

- i. that a critical examination of religious messaging used by religious elites, especially in the Christian genre must be taken into consideration, to understand how they influence perceptions of wealth and poverty among worshippers.
- ii. thorough investigation should be given priority on the specific ways in which religious institutions contribute to or alleviate poverty considering factors such as charitable activities, economic empowerment programs, and social welfare initiatives.
- iii. religious leaders should not only see themselves as spiritual leaders but should explore their roles and responsibilities in addressing poverty issues within their communities, including their influence on public policies, advocacy efforts and resource allocation.
- iv. religious leaders should propose strategies for leveraging religious networks and community structures to empower individuals and communities economically, with a focus on sustainable development and poverty reduction.
- v. there is need to advocate for educational programs and awareness campaigns within religious settings to promote financial literacy, entrepreneurship skills, and responsible stewardship of resources among worshippers.

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USE OF GENERATIVE AI IN LANGUAGE EDITING

In the preparation of this manuscript, generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools were employed strictly for grammar correction, language refinement, and clarity enhancement. Specifically, **ChatGPT (version 4o, developed by OpenAI)** and **Gemini (formerly Bard, developed by Google, version as of June 2025)** were used to assist with sentence restructuring and proofreading. These tools were not used for idea generation, data analysis, or content authorship. All intellectual input, analysis, and interpretations remain those of the author(s). The use of AI was limited to editorial support in line with ethical research and publishing standards.